

1 **Assessment of male reproductive traits in endangered leuciscids from the**
2 **Iberian Peninsula: first attempts to store gametes both at short- and long-**
3 **term**

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15 **Abstract**

16 During the spring of 2022 several endangered leuciscid species (*Anaecypris hispanica*, *Squalius*
17 *aradensis*, *Anachondrostoma Occidentale* and *Iberochondrostoma lusitanicum*) were sampled
18 both at the Vasco da Gama aquarium facilities and in some rivers of the Algarve region, Portugal.
19 Sperm samples were extracted by gentle abdominal pressure and sperm motion parameters
20 were assessed for the first time in four species, using a computerized analysis system. The results
21 obtained showed that spermatozoa kinetic patterns were similar for all 4 species, with high
22 motility and velocity values after the sperm activation time and with a marked decrease after
23 20 seconds. On the other hand, sperm longevity was highly variable between species, with short
24 longevities (around 40 s) for *A. hispanica* and *S. aradensis*, and longer longevities (100-120 s) for
25 *A. occidentale* and *I. lusitanicum*, which could indicate a latitudinal pattern in terms of sperm
26 longevity. At the same time, morphometric analysis was carried out for the four target species,
27 revealing that spermatozoa showed similar sizes and shapes to other external fertilizers
28 belonging to Leuciscidae, with small spherical heads, uniflagellate and without acrosomes.

29 In addition, a short-term gamete storage trial was performed by diluting sperm in 1:9
30 (sperm:extender) and storing them at 4°C. Although the results obtained were uneven among
31 the species studied, the dilution and extender used generated motilities above 40% up to day 4
32 of storage in *S. aradensis* and *I. lusitanicum*, and up to day 1-2 in *A. hispanica* and *A. occidentale*,
33 respectively. Finally, gamete cryopreservation trials were also carried out on these threatened
34 species. Although cryopreserved samples showed significantly lower motility than fresh
35 samples, some protocols generate acceptable percentages of viability, DNA integrity, and sperm
36 motility in some species such as *I. lusitanicum* and *A. occidentale*. The data revealed that the
37 protocol based on 10% DMSO plus 7.5% egg yolk generated the best results.

38 This study is the first to assess the reproductive traits of wild and captive populations of
39 endangered leuciscids endemic from the Iberian Peninsula, describing the spermatozoa kinetics
40 and developing protocols for managing male gametes both in short- and long- term storage.
41 Outcomes will provide new and useful tools to complement the management and conservation
42 of *ex-situ* breeding programs that are being developed for these four endangered species.

43 **Keywords:** Leuciscidae; sperm motility; short-term storage; sperm cryopreservation

44 **1. Introduction**

45 Populations of fish species endemic of the Iberian Peninsula have been declining since the mid-
46 20th century due to factors such as habitat degradation and fragmentation, dredging and
47 draining processes or water quality deterioration (Antunes et al., 2015). In addition to these
48 factors, the typical summer droughts that impose mass killings and genetic bottle necks are an
49 additional extinction risk factor for the Iberian native freshwater species, especially in
50 Mediterranean-type southern streams. With the tendency for global warming in Iberia, these
51 droughts show consistent increase in duration and severity, raising the pressure and the risk of
52 local extinctions (Ribeiro et al., 2020). In this regard, from the 35 Iberian native species belonging
53 to *cyprinidae* and *leuciscidae*, around 70% are already under threat according to International
54 Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN, 2022). This is the case of the target species of that
55 study: the vulnerable Arade chub (*Squalius aradensis*), the endangered Saramugo (*Anaecypris*
56 *hispanica*), the endangered Western ruivaco (*Achondrostoma occidentale*), and the critically
57 endangered Portuguese arched-mouth nase (*Iberochondrostoma lusitanicum*). Although they
58 are mostly small leuciscids with little or no economic value, they play a key role in the aquatic
59 ecosystem, and they are important for biodiversity conservation.

60 Several types of actions have been applied over the past decades for preserving these native
61 fish species, and *in situ* measurements (monitoring programs, ecosystem restoration, etc.) have
62 been successfully complemented with *ex situ* conservation actions (Maceda-Veiga, 2013).
63 Within these achievements, the launch of successful captive breeding programs carried out by
64 the academia, governmental agencies, and non-governmental organizations, allowed to support
65 these several critically endangered Iberian endemic fish (Sousa-Santos et al., 2014). These *ex*-
66 *situ* reproductive programs were able to partially recover natural populations in eminent risk of
67 extinction, by periodically releasing fish and reinforcing the numbers of specific populations or
68 recreating population nuclei restored habitats. Furthermore, the scarce knowledge on the
69 reproductive biology of these species highlights the need to investigate different aspects of their
70 reproductive cycles, such as the duration of the reproductive period, the study of gamete
71 quality, or the possibility for long-term conservation of gametes. In this sense, during the last
72 few years there has been much attention on the development of reproduction biotechnology of
73 rheophilic fish belonging to the family *Leuciscidae* (Cejko et al., 2011; Fernández-Delgado and
74 Herrera, 1995; Kowalski et al., 2012; Pires et al., 2000). Thus, the evaluation of breeders
75 throughout their annual cycle is an indispensable tool to obtain an acceptable yield in terms of
76 larval and fry production, which can be used in the future to repopulate certain areas where
77 these species can be usually found.

78 Following the same line of conservation approach and complementing the *in situ* and *ex situ*
79 preservation efforts, a strategy currently applied in fish management is the creation of genetic

80 resource banks (GRBs) (Martínez-Páramo et al., 2017). GRBs are usually based on
81 cryopreservation techniques, which aim for placing and holding the biological material at ultra-
82 low temperatures for a long period. In that way, the use of GRBs for captive breeding programs
83 make possible to develop several tasks, including *i*) the preservation of the genetic material of
84 endangered species, *ii*) the conservation of certain genetic lines or haplotypes within the same
85 species, or *iii*) the recovery of lost genetic characteristics in some populations or individuals
86 (becoming a wild-phenotypic backup). Even though GRBs are being used systematically in
87 various programs aimed at the conservation of large mammals (felines, canids, or bears), their
88 role as a conservation tool in fish is practically focused on aquaculture production (Mayer, 2019).
89 To date, sperm of more than 200 fish species have been successfully cryopreserved and cryo-
90 protocols for sperm management have been established for freshwater and marine fish species
91 (Betsy and Kumar, 2020). Nevertheless, most of the studies show a great variability between
92 species, populations, individuals from the same population, and even between samples from
93 the same individuals (Blanes-García et al., 2021). Therefore, the design of a cryopreservation
94 protocol must be a meticulous (species-specific) task that should consider the specific
95 characteristics of the gametes of each species to determine the most appropriate parameters
96 for optimizing the cryopreservation process. In the case of species from the family Leuciscidae,
97 some attempts have been successfully applied both short- and long-term gamete storage in
98 species such as the *Leuciscus idus* (Bernáth et al., 2018; Cejko et al., 2022).

99 Following this rationale, this work attempts, as a complement to the *ex-situ* conservation
100 actions, to advance in the reproductive biology and cryobiology of some endangered species
101 belonging to the family Leuciscidae that are catalogued in different degrees of vulnerability
102 according to the IUCN Red List. The output knowledge will help in the future management and
103 conservation of the endangered ichthyofauna of the Iberian Peninsula.

104 **2. Methods**

105 2.1 Ethics statement

106 This study was carried out in strict accordance with the recommendations given in the Guide for
107 the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals of the EU Directive 2010/63/UE, transposed in the
108 Portuguese legislation by the Decree-Law 113/2013, with modifications included in decree-law
109 1/2019, regarding the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. The protocol was
110 approved by the Experimental Animal Ethics Committee from the CCMAR (University of Algarve)
111 and permits for field work were given by ICNF (Fish capture and handling licenses:
112 515/2022/CAPT (CSS), 509/2022/CAPT (VGA) and 506/2022/CAPT (PMG)).

113

114 2.2 Fish sampling

115 To obtain gamete samples of the target species (*A. hispanica*, *S. aradensis*, *A. occidentale* and *I.*
116 *lusitanicum*), several samplings were carried out during the months of March, April, and May
117 2022 both at the Vasco da Gama Aquarium (AVG, Lisbon, Portugal) and in different rivers of the
118 Algarve region, Portugal. Sampling at the aquarium was carried out during tank cleaning days,
119 as individuals had to be taken out for annual monitoring of body condition. During these working
120 days, the specimens of *A. hispanica*, *A. occidentale* and *I. lusitanicum* were removed from their
121 tanks, weighted, measured and the male individuals were separated for sampling.

122 As for the sampling carried out at different points in the Algarve region, targeted electric fishing
123 was carried out with the aim of obtaining specimens of the Arade chub (*S. aradensis*). A portable,
124 battery powered (SUM, Poland) electric fishing equipment was used, carrying out zigzag
125 transects of 15-20 minutes against the current, searching for specimens among the rocks and
126 vegetation. The captured stunned specimens were removed from the environment and, after
127 obtaining the gamete sample, were allowed to recover and returned live to their natural habitat.

128 2.3 Collection of sperm samples

129 For the collection of sperm, the genital area was cleaned with 1% NaCl (pH=8.0, osmolarity=300
130 mOsm/kg) and dried to avoid contamination by faeces, urine or tank water that could activate
131 the sperm. Using the abdominal massage technique performed with two fingers, gamete
132 samples were collected. The number of sperm samples obtained was different for each species:
133 12 for *A. hispanica*, 10 for *S. aradensis*, 52 for *A. occidentale*, and 27 for *I. lusitanicum*. The small
134 amount of sperm obtained (which varied according to the species) was collected with a pipette
135 (P-100) and deposited in 500µl microtubes. The volume of each sample was assessed, and then
136 the sperm was diluted 1:9 (sperm:extender) with SMIS solution (Sperm Motility-Inhibiting Saline
137 Solution). This medium has been used previously in other leuciscid species as an extender
138 (Lahnsteiner and Mansour, 2010) and it is composed by 75 mmol/L NaCl, 70 mmol/L KCl, 2
139 mmol/L CaCl₂, 1 mmol/L MgSO₄, 20 mmol/L Tris. Finally, microtubes with sperm samples were
140 kept in a portable fridge (4 °C) up to 2-3 hours, until the sperm analyses were carried out at
141 laboratory facilities. To measure sperm density, samples were previously diluted in SMIS
142 medium, and finally the dilution was taken for counting the spermatozoa in a hemacytometer.

143 2.4 Assessment of sperm motion parameters

144 The sperm samples (previously diluted 1:9) were activated by mixing 0.5 µl of diluted sperm with
145 4.5 µL of freshwater of their environments (0-50 mOsm/kg, pH=7.0-8.0) in a Makler Chamber
146 (10 µm depth). Samples were analysed with ISAS (Integrated Semen Analysis System) software,
147 capturing 0.5 second video sequences at 25 fps (frames per second) using a camera attached to
148 a phase contrast microscope (Nikon Eclipse E200) through 10x lens. All the motility analyses
149 were performed in triplicate. Sperm samples with motility above 60% were selected for

150 characterized the sperm motion parameters and kinetic patterns of each species: 7 for *A.*
151 *hispanica*, 7 for *S. aradensis*, 11 for *A. occidentale*, and 13 for *I. lusitanicum*.

152 The parameters used in this study were total motility (MOT, %), defined as the percentage of
153 motile cells in the sample; progressive motility (pMOT, %), defined as the percentage of
154 spermatozoa moving essentially in a straight line; curvilinear velocity (VCL, $\mu\text{m/s}$), defined as the
155 total distance travelled by the sperm head per unit time; the rectilinear velocity (VSL, $\mu\text{m/s}$),
156 determined from the straight-line distance between the first and last point of its trajectory; and
157 the percentage of fast (VAP > 100 $\mu\text{m/s}$), medium (VAP = 50-100 $\mu\text{m/s}$) and slow (VAP = 10-50
158 $\mu\text{m/s}$) spermatozoa, where VAP (mean trajectory velocity), is defined as the distance travelled
159 by the spermatozoa along the mean trajectory. Sperm samples were considered motile if their
160 total motility was over 10%.

161 2.5 Study of morphological parameters

162 Sperm samples were fixed in 1% glutaraldehyde for subsequent analysis with a phase contrast
163 optical microscope (Nikon Eclipse E200) using a 100x lens. Photographs of 50 spermatozoa from
164 5 individuals for each species were taken with a camera (VisiCam 16 Plus VWR) connected to the
165 microscope. The images obtained were analysed with ImageJ software, and measurements of
166 the sperm head and flagella were taken. Regarding spermatozoa head measurements, several
167 size variables such as length (L, μm), width (W, μm), area (A, μm^2), and perimeter (P, μm) and
168 shape variables such as ellipticity (L/W) were also measured.

169 2.6 Short- and long- term preservation protocols

170 Sperm samples with motility above 60% were selected for carrying out the short-term
171 preservation trial. Sperm samples were stored in the refrigerator (4°C) diluted at 1:9
172 (sperm:SMIS), with a final concentration ranging from 3-5x10⁸ spz/mL in *A. hispanica*, 1-2x10⁸
173 spz/mL in *S. aradensis*, 6-8x10⁸ spz/mL in *A. occidentale*, and 5-6x10⁸ spz/mL in *I. lusitanicum*.
174 Samples were stored in 500 μl microtubes (closed) without shaking, and they were analysed
175 every 24 hours with ISAS software (see section 2.3) until their total motility dropped below 5%.

176 Regarding cryopreservation trials, sperm samples with motility greater than 60% (for *A.*
177 *hispanica* and *I. lusitanicum*), 50% (for *A. occidentale*), and 40% (for *S. aradensis*) were selected
178 for cryopreservation assays. Samples were diluted 1:8 (sperm:extender) in a SIMS solution and
179 different concentrations (from 5 to 10%) of internal (methanol, MET; dimethyl sulfoxide, DMSO;
180 and glycerol, GLY) and external (egg yolk, EY) cryoprotectants were tested. Final concentrations
181 of sperm samples before freezing ranged from 3-5x10⁸ spz/mL in *A. hispanica*, 1-2x10⁸ spz/mL
182 in *S. aradensis*, 6-8x10⁸ spz/mL in *A. occidentale*, and 5-6x10⁸ spz/mL in *I. lusitanicum*. Samples
183 were immediately packed in straws of 250 μl . Between two and three straws from each
184 specimen were used, according to the available sperm volume. The diluted samples were then
185 incubated for 5 min at 4 °C. The freezing condition was created by placing the straws on a

186 floating structure 2 cm over the liquid nitrogen (LN) for 5 min in a polystyrene box, and then by
187 dropping them into the LN. For the thawing process, the straws were thawed at 25°C for 15
188 seconds. The motility patterns were again analysed by triplicate using the ISAS software (see
189 section 2.3), and further analyses were carried out for assessing the gamete viability and the
190 DNA fragmentation.

191 2.7 Gamete viability

192 Cell viability was conducted for the cryopreservation trial in every fresh and thawed sample
193 using a fluorescence kit (LIVE/DEAD Sperm Viability Kit, Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA)
194 containing SYBR 14 and propidium iodide (PI). For each sample, previously diluted at 1:200
195 (sperm:extender), 0.5 µL of SYBR 14 (final concentration 100 nM) and 2 µL of PI (final
196 concentration 12 µM) were added to 50 µL of fresh or thawed sperm samples and incubated at
197 room temperature and darkness for 10 min. Thereafter, each sample was placed on a slide for
198 analysis in a fluorescence microscope. Photographs of fresh and thawed samples were taken
199 with a VisiCam 16 Plus VWR camera at 20x magnification. Then 100 cells were counted using
200 ImageJ software and the number of live cells (green) and dead cells (red) was calculated.

201 2.8 DNA fragmentation (Comet assay)

202 The protocol used was developed by Cabrita *et al.* (2005) with some modifications to fit the
203 target species. Agarose coated slides were used to support 50ul of cells previously embedded in
204 low-melting agarose. After incubation in a lysis solution and electrophoresis, the samples were
205 incubated in a neutralisation solution and finally fixed with ethanol. Once dried and fixed, the
206 samples were stained with PI and observed with a 40x objective on a fluorescence microscope.
207 Photographs were taken with Wavelmage software and then cell damage was analysed with
208 Komet6 brand. Measurements of 100 cells per male and treatment were taken to compare the
209 cell damage of fresh and cryopreserved samples. The parameter analysed was the percentage
210 of DNA in the tail (% DNAt).

211 2.9 Statistical analysis

212 The mean ± standard error was calculated for all sperm quantity and quality parameters.
213 Shapiro-Wilk and Levene tests were used to check the normality of data distribution and
214 variance homogeneity, respectively. For non-normal distributions of percentage values, the data
215 were transformed using arc-sin transformation prior to statistical analysis. Univariate General
216 Linear Model (GLM) and Student-Newman-Keuls (SNK) tests were used to analyze the sperm
217 kinetic parameters along post-activation times. One-way ANOVA was used to analyze the
218 morphometric parameters and the different cryopreservation protocols. Significant differences
219 were detected when *p-value*<0.05. All statistical analyses were performed using the statistical
220 package SPSS version 24.0 for Windows software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

221 **3. Results**

222 **3.1 Sperm density, volume, and motility**

223 The samples obtained showed a wide range of spermatozoa densities among the species studied
224 (Fig. 1; and Supplementary Data), ranging from 5×10^8 spz/mL in *A. hispanica* to more than 1×10^{10}
225 in the case of *A. occidentale* (Fig. 1D). In all samples of *S. aradensis* the density values were
226 between $1-4 \times 10^9$ spz/mL, while in the rest of the species the variability was much higher. In
227 terms of volume, *A. occidentale* and *I. lusitanicum* showed a similar distribution with a very wide
228 volume range, from less than 5 μ L to more than 50 μ L per individual (Fig. 1C' and 1D'). *A.*
229 *hispanica* individuals generated the smallest volumes (Fig. 1A'), with most samples (~80%)
230 presenting volumes between 5 and 10 μ L. In contrast, *S. aradensis* individuals showed high
231 sperm volumes and all samples collected were between 100 and 460 μ L (Supplementary Data).
232 The histograms obtained for the sperm motility were similar for all species, with a relatively high
233 percentage of males (40-60%) showing good quality samples (between 50-75% of motile cells),
234 and 10-30% of males showing high quality sperm samples (motility values over 75%).

235 All the statistical values (mean; standard deviation; standard error; minimum and maximum
236 values; and lower and upper confidence intervals at 95%) regarding sperm density, volume, and
237 motility can be consulted in Supplementary Material.

238 **Figure 1.** Histograms of the sperm density, sperm volume and sperm motility of A) *A. hispanica*
239 (n=12), B) *S. aradensis* (n=8), C) *A. occidentale* (n=30), and D) *I. lusitanicum* (n=31).
240

241 3.2 Sperm motion parameters over time

242 All four species showed high motility (around 70-80%) during the first 5-10 seconds post-
 243 activation, with a marked and significant decrease at 20 seconds in all species (Fig. 2). The
 244 motility patterns were very similar in *A. hispanica* and *S. aradensis*, while the pattern of *A.*
 245 *occidentale* was similar to *I. lusitanicum*. The most notable difference in the sperm motion
 246 parameters was in the swimming time: the species with the longest sperm duration was *I.*
 247 *lusitanicum* (120 seconds) and the species with the shortest longevity was *S. aradensis* (40
 248 seconds).

249

250 **Figure 2.** Total (MOT) and progressive (pMOT) motility of A) *A. hispanica* (n=7), B) *S. aradensis*
 251 (n=7), C) *A. occidentale* (n=11), and D) *I. lusitanicum* (n=13) at different post activation times
 252 Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error. Letters indicate significant differences between
 253 post-activation times.

254 Regarding sperm kinetics (Fig. 3), all four species showed a high percentage of fast spermatozoa
 255 (>60%) during the first 5 seconds post-activation. However, from 10 seconds post-activation, the
 256 percentage of fast spermatozoa decreased to less than 30% in the case of *A. occidentale* and *I.*
 257 *lusitanicum*; and to less than 10% in *A. hispanica* and *S. aradensis*.

258

259 **Figure 3.** Percentage of fast, medium, and slow spermatozoa in A) *A. hispanica* (n=7), B) *S.*
 260 *aradensis* (n=7), C) *A. occidentale* (n=11), and D) *I. lusitanicum* (n=13) at different post activation
 261 times. Arrows indicates the first significant difference on fast spermatozoa from the sperm
 262 activation point (5s).

263 3.3 Sperm morphology

264 The different morphometric parameters studied using ImageJ software showed significant
 265 differences between the species studied (Table 1). The species with the largest spermatozoa
 266 (head and flagellum) was *A. occidentale*, with significant differences in almost all morphometric
 267 parameters compared to the other 3 species. *A. hispanica* and *S. aradensis* had the smallest
 268 spermatozoa, with no marked differences between them but with significant differences
 269 compared to the other two species (*A. occidentale* and *I. lusitanicum*). Figure 4 shows optical
 270 microscope photographs (100X) of the spermatozoa of all species studied. All of them showed a
 271 similar structure with a spherical head (1), a middle part (2) and a flagellum (3).

272 **Table 1.** Morphometric parameters of the head and flagellum of spermatozoa of *A. hispanica*,
 273 *S. aradensis*, *A. occidentale*, and *I. lusitanicum* measured with ImageJ software using a light
 274 microscopy (n=50 spermatozoa of 5 specimens). Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error
 275 and letters mean significant differences between species.

	<i>A. hispanica</i>	<i>S. aradensis</i>	<i>A. occidentale</i>	<i>I. lusitanicum</i>
Area (μm^2)	3.83 \pm 0.06 c	3.63 \pm 0.06 c	5.13 \pm 0.03 a	4.85 \pm 0.10 b
Perimeter (μm)	9.84 \pm 0.18 c	9.41 \pm 0.19 c	13.88 \pm 0.41 a	11.06 \pm 0.12 b
Width (μm)	2.00 \pm 0.00 b	2.00 \pm 0.00 b	2.21 \pm 0.03 a	2.08 \pm 0.03 b
Length (μm)	2.04 \pm 0.02 b	2.04 \pm 0.01 b	2.90 \pm 0.02 a	2.83 \pm 0.07 a
Ellipticity	0.93 \pm 0.01 a	0.93 \pm 0.00 a	0.90 \pm 0.01 b	0.90 \pm 0.00 b
Flagellum	26.4 \pm 3.7 b	23.1 \pm 1.2 c	31.1 \pm 1.5 a	28.6 \pm 1.7 ab

1=Head sperm; 2=Mid piece and 3= Flagellum

276

277 **Figure 4.** Spermatozoa morphology of *A. hispanica* (A), *S. aradensis* (B), *A. occidentale* (C) and *I.*
 278 *lusitanicum* (D). Pictures A and B were taken using the 100x lens and pictures C and D using the
 279 40x lens. Scale bar is showed in the pictures.

280 3.4 Short-term gamete preservation

281 The sperm quality of samples diluted (1:9 in SMIS) and stored at 4°C was studied over 5 days of
 282 storage (Fig. 5). In relation to sperm motility, 3 of 4 species studied (*A. hispanica*, *A. occidentale*,
 283 and *I. lusitanicum*) suffered a significant decrease in the percentage of motile spermatozoa after
 284 24 hours of storage. However, in some species such as *S. aradensis* and *I. lusitanicum*, sperm
 285 motility did not decrease drastically over time, even presenting values of more than 40% of
 286 motile spermatozoa at 4 days of storage (Fig. 5B and 5D).

287 In relation to velocities (fast, medium, and slow spermatozoa), the results showed a progressive
 288 drop in the number of fast spermatozoa over time in all species (and therefore an increase in
 289 the percentage of slow and medium spermatozoa). However, this drop was very marked in
 290 species such as *S. aradensis* and *A. occidentale* (with significant differences on day 1) and very
 291 mild in species such as *I. lusitanicum*, which showed a significantly lower percentage of fast
 292 spermatozoa on day 3 of storage.

293

294 **Figure 5.** Percentage of total motility (dot lines) and the fast, medium, and slow spermatozoa
 295 over storage time (1 to 5 days) in A) *A. hispanica* (n=7), B) *S. aradensis* (n=7), C) *A. occidentale*
 296 (n=11), and D) *I. lusitanicum* (n=13), at different post activation times. Data are expressed as
 297 mean \pm standard error. Letters indicate significant differences between post activation times;
 298 and arrows indicates the first significant difference on fast spermatozoa from the sperm
 299 activation point (5s).

300 Finally, it is important to note that in the case of *A. hispanica* it was not possible to study short-
 301 term preservation for more than two days, as due to the small volume generated by this species
 302 there was not enough sample volume for a continuous evaluation.

303 3.5 Cryopreservation trials

304 Results from the cryopreservation trials showed that the cryopreservation process caused a
 305 reduction of the sperm viability and motility parameters (irrespective of the protocol used) in all
 306 the species studied (Table 2). In the case of *A. hispanica*, protocols based on 10% methanol and
 307 DMSO) generated significant differences in viability (from 70% in the control group to 20% in
 308 cryopreserved samples), DNA fragmentation (comet assay) and motility (with values from 75%
 309 in the control group to 1-3% in cryopreserved samples). In the case of *I. lusitanicum*, although
 310 all the protocols tested also significantly decreased the gamete quality, the addition of 7.5% egg
 311 yolk to a 10% DMSO-based protocol significantly improved the motility compared to the other
 312 protocols used. In this case, the 10% DMSO plus 7.5% egg yolk generated motility values of 15-
 313 20%, which was the highest value in all protocols and species studied during the
 314 cryopreservation trials. In the case of *S. aradensis* and considering that the initial samples did
 315 not show high motility values (45-50%), the protocols tested did not generated good cell viability

316 and motility values. Finally, regarding *A. occidentale*, it was again observed that the addition of
 317 egg yolk to a protocol based on 10% DMSO significantly improved motility with respect to the
 318 rest of the protocols used. In this case, the protocol based on 10% DMSO plus 7.5% egg yolk
 319 produced motility values of 9.2% and viabilities of 24.5%.

320 **Table 2.** Effects of the different gamete cryopreservation protocols applied in *A. hispanica* (n=5),
 321 *S. aradensis* (n=5), *A. occidentale* (n=7), and *I. lusitanicum* (n=9) on viability, DNA fragmentation
 322 and spermatozoa motility. Letters indicate significant differences between the protocols used
 323 (mean values± SEM).

Species	Protocol	Viability	SEM	DNA frag.	SEM	Motility	SEM
<i>A. hispanica</i>	Control	73.6 a	8.6	15.3 a	0.7	74.4 a	2.8
	DMSO-10	23.3 b	2.1	26.5 b	0.4	3.5 b	3.0
	METH-10	20.5 b	4.5	29.3 b	3.7	1.5 b	0.8
<i>I. lusitanicum</i>	Control	65.6 a	4.4	18.5 a	1.0	83.1 a	2.4
	DMSO-10	11.9 c	1.9	24.3 b	1.4	1.0 c	0.4
	METH-10	23.6 b	2.5	18.5 a	1.8	1.4 c	0.2
	DMSO-10 + EGG-7.5	33.0 b	2.5	16.0 a	1.4	16.8 b	2.5
	EGG-15	25.9 b	4.2	20.1 a	1.5	0.2 c	0.1
<i>S. aradensis</i>	Control	45.0 a	4.9	17.1 a	0.6	47.5 a	2.4
	DMSO-5	10.0 b	4.3	20.3 a	0.7	0.6 b	0.1
	DMSO-10	19.5 b	5.7	15.5 a	0.0	1.1 b	0.2
	DMSO-10 + EGG-10	8.2 b	1.9	20.2 a	1.2	2.1 b	0.7
<i>A. occidentale</i>	Control	75.7 a	4.6	19.1 a	0.9	56.7 a	6.5
	DMSO-5	24.7 b	6.3	17.6 a	1.4	2.0 c	0.5
	DMSO-5 + EGG-10	12.6 c	1.4	17.4 a	1.8	2.2 c	0.7
	DMSO-10 + EGG-7.5	24.7 b	6.3	18.6 a	1.4	9.2 b	0.9
	GLY-5	11.3 c	3.8	18.6 a	2.9	1.1 c	0.3
	GLY-5 + EGG-10	7.5 c	0.5	20.9 a	5.0	1.1 c	0.2
	GLY-15	7.0 c	0.0	29.2 b	0.0	0.0 c	0.0

325 4. Discussion

326 Sperm quantity and quality

327 One of the factors to be considered when carrying out *ex situ* conservation programmes is the
 328 quantity and quality of the gametes produced by the breeders. During this work, in the four
 329 species studied, the sperm density values obtained ranged from 2×10^9 to 1×10^{10} spz/mL. These
 330 results are in line with those obtained by other authors in species belonging to the family
 331 Leuciscidae in Central Europe and north America. For example, densities of 1×10^{10} spz/mL were
 332 obtained in specimens of *Rhynchocypris percunurus* (Dietrich et al., 2011), sperm densities of $7-$
 333 13×10^9 spz/mL were reported in *Leuciscus idus* (Cejko et al., 2022); and finally, in individuals of
 334 *Squalis cephalus*, densities between $5-7 \times 10^9$ spz/mL were reported by (Cejko and Krejszef, 2016).
 335 Regarding sperm volume, the amount of milt obtained varied considerably among the
 336 species. The lowest sperm volume samples were obtained from *A. hispanica* (5-10 μ l), followed
 337 by *A. occidentale* and *I. lusitanicum* (5-50 μ l), and finally *S. aradensis*, which was the species that
 338 generated the highest volumes, with some wild showing samples with more than 400 μ l. That

339 huge variability found in sperm volumes between species could be explained, on the one hand,
340 by the size (weight and length) of the specimens. In that sense, the lowest volumes were found
341 in *A. hispanica*, which showed tiny mean weights and lengths of 1.1 ± 0.2 grams and 48.3 ± 5.3
342 mm, respectively. At the other extreme we had the wild population *S. aradensis*, which released
343 average sperm volumes of 218.8 ± 45.3 μ L but showing weights and lengths of 14.7 ± 4.2 grams
344 and 108.7 ± 11.2 mm, respectively. On the other hand, this huge variability in sperm volumes is
345 also reported in the literature linked to the family Leuciscidae. In that sense, some studies
346 reported sperm volumes ranging from 0.5 to 6 μ L in *P. promelas* (Hala et al., 2009; Martinovic-
347 Weigelt et al., 2012), around 10 μ L in specimens of *E. percnurus* (Dietrich et al., 2011), and
348 ranging from 0.5 to 2.5 ml in *Alburnus alburnus* (Lahnsteiner et al., 1996). Finally, and thinking
349 in aquaculture issues, to solve the problem of having such low volumes in some species of
350 Leuciscidae family (e.g. *A. hispanica*), for further studies it would be interesting to increase the
351 net gamete production (binomial density-volume) applying hormonal treatments for stimulate
352 the spermiation process. In that sense, this strategy has been already applied in other leuciscid
353 species with great results both in *Leuciscus leuciscus* (Cejko et al., 2012) or *Leuciscus cephalus*
354 (Cejko and Krejszef, 2016).

355 In addition to sperm quantity parameters (density and volume), when referring to the sperm
356 quality the most used parameter has been the spermatozoa motility (Gallego and Asturiano,
357 2018). In this work we present for the first time the sperm kinetic parameters of four leuciscid
358 species (*A. hispanica*, *S. aradensis*, *A. occidentale* and *I. lusitanicum*) analysed using a
359 computerised gamete analysis system (ISAS). In general, for the 4 target species, it was observed
360 that motility and velocity values were high after freshwater activation (5-10 seconds), with a
361 marked decrease after 20 seconds. These motion patterns are similar to other freshwater
362 species of closer families, such as cyprinidae (Alavi et al., 2009) or percidae (Alavi et al., 2010).
363 However, there are only few studies of sperm kinetics over time in fish belonging to the family
364 Leuciscidae. In that sense, a study carried out in the common murre (*A. alburnus*), showed that
365 the kinetic pattern was not so similar to the species studied. In that case, the sperm of *A.*
366 *Alburnus* reached the maximum motility at 45-50 seconds post-activation and has a longevity of
367 about 5 minutes (Lahnsteiner et al., 1996). In addition, a study carried out by Bernáth et al.
368 (2018) on the ide (*L. leuciscus*) showed that longevity of sperm movement did not show a
369 significant decline in sperm motion parameters for up to 120 s. Similar results were also
370 published by Kowalski et al. (2012) on the ide, which sperm motility ranged from 50 to 40%
371 (without big differences) on during the whole activation time.

372 Regarding to longevity – or how long spermatozoa move – the values for the species studied are
373 in the range of other freshwater species, which typically show values of less than 2 minutes
374 (Browne et al., 2015). In our study, sperm samples from *A. hispanica* and *S. aradensis* had much
375 less longevity (40-60 seconds) than samples from *A. occidentale* and *I. lusitanicum* (100-120

376 seconds). The differences found between these species could be due to the reproductive biology
377 of each species, due to sperm kinetic parameters (motility, speed, and longevity) are usually
378 closely linked to the reproductive behaviour of the species (Gallego et al., 2014). In that sense
379 (and searching for answers regarding the spermatozoa kinetic differences between species), it
380 would be also possible the existence of a latitudinal gradient from the north to the south species.
381 In that sense, for the southern species (more affected by the loss of longitudinal connectivity
382 imposed by increasingly longer and more intense droughts), their recruitment during the
383 spawning season could be affected the sperm swimming time and other reproductive traits, while
384 in the northern species (not so affected by desertification events), the reproductive traits would
385 not be so affected.

386 In relation to morphology study, the analyses carried out revealed that the spermatozoa of the
387 four species studied presented a morphology similar to other cyprinids and leuciscids species
388 with external fertilisation, with small sized cells, spherical head, a middle piece and uniflagellate
389 (Neznanova, 2012). The sperm morphology of other leuciscid and cyprinid species has been
390 characterised, for example, in *E. percunurus*, where the sperm head is 1.88 μm long and 2.03 μm
391 wide (Dietrich et al., 2014) or in species such as *Chondrostoma nasus* and *Rutilus meidingerii*
392 (Fürböck et al., 2010). In the case of cyprinidae species, the sperm head of *B. barbatus* was 1.80
393 μm (Alavi et al., 2008), while in *C. carpio* the sperm head width varied from 1.3 to 2.0 μm (Verma
394 et al., 2009). Therefore, results published by other authors in other phylogenetically close groups
395 are similar in terms of sperm head dimensions.

396 Short- and long-term gamete storage

397 As two main approaches for gamete storage, short-term storage refers to keeping gametes at
398 above zero temperatures, while long-term storage infers preservation of gametes at below zero
399 temperatures. Short-term storage, ranging from days to weeks, provides some advantages for
400 aquaculture practice in terms of many useful features (e.g., sex synchronization, shipping of
401 gametes, etc.), and can be carried out both in spermatozoa and eggs (Inanan, 2020). During this
402 work, we have attempted to preserve male gametes from four endangered leuciscid species
403 from the Iberian Peninsula in the short-term storage. Although the results obtained were
404 uneven among the species studied, dilution (1:9) and the use of SMIS as extender generated
405 motilities higher than 40% up to the 4th day of storage in *S. aradensis* and *I. lusitanicum*. This
406 information represents an important advance in the management of these species, as the
407 handling of broodstock for certain tasks involving *in vitro* fertilisation processes could be
408 reduced, decreasing the stress to which individuals are subjected during sampling. Some trials
409 have been carried out in other leuciscid species such as the ide (*L. leuciscus*), where Sarosiek et
410 al. (2012) reported sperm motilities from 46% to 33% after 1-day storage and reaching 13% after
411 5-days storage. However, in another trial carried out on the ide more recently, Bernáth et al.

412 (2018) reported significant decreases of chilled storage on sperm motility (from 50 to 5%) just
413 at 2-days storage. In that sense, the differences found between those trials could be explained
414 due the type of extender used (e.g., SMIS *versus* TLP) and the sperm:extender ratio applied (1:3
415 *versus* 1:9). Considering all the trials, seems to be evident that to dilute the sperm is an essential
416 premise for keep the sperm motility as long as possible, always using a proper extender similar
417 to the seminal plasma composition of target species. In other phylogenetically close species such
418 as *R. percnurus*, Short-term storage of semen was successfully applied to secure 50% sperm
419 motility for 9 days in VRT buffer (Dietrich et al., 2015).

420 Despite the good results obtained in this study, it is important to note that during storage of the
421 samples in the refrigerator, sedimentation occurred in almost all species. *S. aradensis* samples
422 had a strong tendency to form clumps at the bottom of the vials over the days, and the
423 appearance of these clumps was linked to a sharp drop in sperm motility. In that sense, other
424 studies have shown that continuous gentle agitation during storage improves quality
425 parameters during the first days or weeks by preventing the formation of clumps (Herranz-
426 Jurdado et al., 2019). Therefore, in future studies, it would be interesting to test the gentle
427 mixing of samples (using an electronic shaker) for extending the sperm quality and viability over
428 time (Herranz-Jurdado et al., 2019). As complementary methods, another way to improve short-
429 term preservation would be the addition of antibiotics. In that sense, Cejko et al. (2022) retained
430 in ide sperm the motility and fertilization capacity over 14 days at 4 °C diluting the sperm with
431 TLP supplemented with penicillin/streptomycin, regardless of the dilution ratio used.

432 Regarding long-term (cryopreservation) storage trials, cryopreserved samples of all species
433 showed lower motility than fresh samples, reaching maximum percentages of 15-20% of motile
434 cells after thawing in the best of the protocols. However, the data obtained indicated that, in
435 general, and for all species studied, the best results in kinetic parameters were obtained using a
436 protocol based on 10% DMSO (used as internal cryoprotectant) with 7.5% egg yolk (used as
437 external cryoprotectant). As far as we know, there are only few reports about the gamete
438 cryopreservation of leuciscid species. One of them was carried out in the lake minnow (*E.*
439 *percunurus*), and the highest motility value of cryopreserved sperm was obtained applying
440 methanol and DMSO as cryoprotectants in Tris-glucose buffer (Dietrich et al., 2015). Other study
441 carried out by Bernáth et al. (2018) on the ide (*L. leuciscus*), showed no significant differences
442 between fresh and cryopreserved sperm using 10% methanol, but the variability between
443 sample were too high (pMOT; fresh sperm: $49 \pm 19\%$ *versus* and cryopreserved sperm:
444 $22 \pm 22\%$). Our results agree with work published by other authors on other cyprinid species. In
445 this regard, cryopreservation of *Chalcalburnus chalcoides* gametes using 10% DMSO combined
446 with 5% egg yolk generated post-thaw motilities of up to 30% (Lahnsteiner et al., 2000). Finally,
447 the use of 10% DMSO with 10% egg yolk in *Aspius aspius* generated values of 25% motile cells
448 after thawing (Babiak et al., 1998). On the other hand, Urbányi *et al.*, (2006) also demonstrated

449 the efficacy of using methanol and DMSO as cryoprotectants in four different cyprinid species
450 (*R. rutilus*, *A. brama*, *B. bjoerkna*, *B. barbuis*). However, the use of methanol as a cryoprotectant
451 during this study did not generate good motility and viability values in any of the species. Even
452 so, for further studies it seems interesting to explore the possibility of mixing methanol with
453 external cryoprotectants (e.g., sugars or egg yolk) with the aim to improve the results obtained.
454 In addition to motility as a bioindicator of sperm quality, different analyses were also performed
455 to assess sperm cell integrity in both fresh and cryopreserved samples: cell viability and the
456 "Comet assay". Regarding cell viability, the highest value was obtained in *I. lusitanicum* using the
457 10% DMSO and 7.5% egg yolk protocol with results of 30-35% live cells after cryopreservation.
458 These results are similar to those obtained in other species: with values close to 35% viability in
459 *Salmo salar* (Kommisrud et al., 2020), 30% in *Silurus glanis* (Linhart et al., 2005). On the other
460 hand, the Comet Assay was used to assess differences in DNA integrity before and after
461 cryopreservation. Cell damage was higher in cryopreserved samples than in fresh samples in
462 species such as *A. hispanica* and *I. lusitanicum*, where both cryoprotectants (DMSO and
463 methanol) generated similar percentages of DNA damage between 20 and 25%. In contrast,
464 cryopreserved samples of *S. aradensis* and *A. occidentale* showed no significant differences
465 compared to control samples using methanol or DMSO as cryoprotectants. However, the use of
466 5% glycerol as cryoprotectant generated the highest degradation values throughout the study.
467 In other studies, carried out on commercial species, DNA degradation has been observed with
468 similar values (although slightly higher) of around 30% in *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (Cabrita et al.,
469 2005), 35% in *Sparus aurata* (Cabrita et al., 2005) and 38% in *Dicentrarchus labrax* (Zilli et al.,
470 2003). Finally, it is important to note that the storage of gametes of threatened species is a
471 scientific challenge, but it is important not to consider gene banks as static stores of biodiversity
472 (Herraez et al., 2011). In this sense, the design of the first spermatozoa cryopreservation
473 protocols for *A. hispanica*, *S. aradensis*, *I. lusitanicum* and *A. occidentale* should be considered
474 only as a starting point, with the final goal of optimising and standardising current protocols to
475 generate a gene bank focused on and for the *in situ* and *ex situ* conservation of these species.

476 **5. Conclusions**

477 To sum up, this study improves our knowledge of the reproductive biology of four endangered
478 leuciscid species from the Iberian Peninsula (*A. hispanica*, *S. aradensis*, *A. occidentale* and *I.*
479 *lusitanicum*), by reporting both sperm motion parameters and spermatozoa morphometric
480 features in all of them. In addition, this study is the first of its kind to achieve gamete
481 cryopreservation of these species, developing protocols for managing male gametes both in
482 short- and long- term storage. Outcomes will provide new and useful tools to complement the
483 management and conservation of *ex-situ* breeding programs that are being developed on these
484 four endangered species.

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492 **Ethical Approval**

493 This study was carried out in strict accordance with the recommendations given in the Guide for
494 the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals of the EU Directive 2010/63/UE, transposed in the
495 Portuguese legislation by the Decree-Law 113/2013, with modifications included in decree-law
496 1/2019, regarding the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. The protocol was
497 approved by the Experimental Animal Ethics Committee from the CCMAR (University of Algarve)
498 and permits for field work were given by ICNF (Fish capture and handling licenses:
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500 **Competing Interests**

501 The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

502 **Consent to participate and consent to publication**

503 Not applicable

504 **Author Contributions**

505 **Ana Hernández-Rodríguez:** Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Writing –
506 Original Draft, Visualization. **Carla Sousa-Santos:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing - Review
507 & Editing. **Fátima Gil:** Resources, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing. **Elsa**
508 **Cabrita:** Project Administration, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing. **Pedro M. Guerreiro:**
509 Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing; **V. Gallego:** Conceptualization, Validation,
510 Methodology, Investigation, Resources, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision.

511 **Data Availability Statement.**

512 CRYO-FISH will follow the general politics of EU (H2020 Work Programme 2018-2020), helping
513 to promote the policy goals of open innovation, open science and open to the world (three O's),
514 and our DMP identifies just one category of data and materials: “free available data”. There is a

515 central repository of these data and materials on the [CRYO-FISH web page](#) and more data are
516 available from the authors upon reasonable request

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